

The Main Types of Modern Eloquence Are

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Abstract. *Oratory is the art of practical verbal influence, which gives us the opportunity to masterfully use the word as an instrument of thought and persuasion. The goal of rhetoric as a science has become the teaching of free, expedient and convincing speech.*

Key words: *lecture, socio-political eloquence, modern rhetoric, public speech.*

The genera and types of eloquence are distinguished depending on the sphere of communication corresponding to one of the main functions of speech: communication, communication and impact. There are several areas of communication: scientific, business, information and propaganda, and social and household. For example, a university lecture or a scientific report can be attributed to the first, a diplomatic speech or a speech at a congress to the second, a military—patriotic speech or a rally speech to the third, an anniversary (commendatory) speech or a table speech (toast) to the fourth. Of course, such a division is not absolute. For example, a speech on a socio-economic topic can serve the scientific sphere (a scientific report), the business sphere (a report at a congress), the information and propaganda sphere (a speech by a propagandist in a group of listeners). They will also have common features in shape. In modern practice of public communication, the following types of eloquence are distinguished: socio-political, academic, judicial, social, spiritual (church theological). The kind of eloquence is an area of oratory characterized by the presence of a certain object of speech, a specific system of its analysis and evaluation. The result of further differentiation based on more specific features are types or genres. This classification is situational and thematic in nature, since, firstly, the situation of the speech is taken into account, and secondly, the topic and purpose of the speech. Socio-political eloquence includes speeches on socio-political, politico-economic, socio-cultural, ethical and moral topics, speeches on scientific and technological progress, reports at congresses, meetings, conferences, diplomatic, political, military-patriotic, rallying, agitational, parliamentary speeches. Some genres of eloquence have features of the official business and scientific style, since they are based on official documents. In such speeches, the situation in the country and events in the world are analyzed, their main purpose is to give listeners specific information. These public statements contain facts of a political, economic nature, etc., assess current events, make recommendations, and make a report on the work done. These speeches may be devoted to topical issues or may be conscriptive, explanatory, programmatic and theoretical in nature. The choice and use of language tools depends primarily on the topic and the target setting of the speech. Some kind of political speeches are characterized by those stylistic features that characterize the official style: impersonality or a weak manifestation of personality, book coloring, functionally colored vocabulary, political vocabulary, political, economic terms. Other political speeches use a wide variety of visual and emotional means to achieve the desired effect for the speaker. For example, in rallying speeches with a call-up orientation, colloquial vocabulary and syntax are often used. Modern rhetoric, accumulating all the achievements of psychology, text linguistics, sociolinguistics, logic, and speech culture, is the science of expedient, effective, and harmonious speech. The main purpose of studying

rhetoric is practical (mastery of the art of an expedient persuasive word). The art of words is the most necessary, but also the most difficult of all the arts, so studying it requires very serious work. The development of rhetoric is impossible without fluency in the literary language, without knowledge of history, philosophy, literature, the basics of law, without acquaintance with other branches of knowledge, in other words - without comprehensive erudition. Otherwise, the rhetoric turns into the most ordinary unnecessary nonsense. To increase the degree of erudition, everyone who wants to become serious should make active personal efforts aimed at self-education also outside the framework of studying this course. To really learn how to build a competent and convincing written and oral public speech, it is necessary:

- 1) to understand how argumentation works, that is, to know the theory;
- 2) to read and analyze works that are a kind of model of classical authors in order to develop the ability to understand the work of the word;
- 3) to practice building various kinds of oral and written texts, that is, to learn the skills of independent creative work with the word;
- 4) to speak and to write publicly in the real circumstances of public life.

The first three tasks are solved in the rhetoric training course, and the fourth, the main task, is in the course of the rhetorician's professional activity. The rhetoric training course is just the foundation of a speaker's professional competence. Public speech is a monologue in form, but in essence it is a dialogue. And this creates additional difficulties for the speaker. If the interlocutor's reaction is expressed very definitely in a dialogue, then in a public speech it should be guessed from the behavior of the listeners, their gestures, remarks, and eye expressions. This should be done at the same time as making a speech. And here another difficulty comes into play — linguistic, or linguistic. The need to "cover a more extensive thematic content" complicates the syntax of a monologue compared to a dialogue: sentences become structurally more complex; combining them into a coherent piece of text is multi-step; in order to maintain the structural and stylistic unity of the text as a whole, the speaker is forced to keep both the end and the beginning of the utterance in the field of attention.

The presentation should consist of three parts:

1. Introduction.
2. The main part.
3. Conclusion.

Approximate time distribution:

- introduction – 10-15%;
- the main part is 60-65%;
- conclusion – 20-30%.

1. Introduction. The introduction is an important part, as it is most remembered by the listeners, so it should be carefully thought out. It includes: an explanation of the purpose, the title of the report and a decoding of the subtitle in order to accurately determine the content of the speech, a clear definition of the core idea. We don't want to "linger" on the introduction – it should be brief. When preparing the introduction, you should choose a topic that aims to arouse the interest of the public.

2. The main part. The main part is a comprehensive justification of the main thesis. Some variants of the systematic construction of the argument: - problematic presentation (identification and analysis of contradictions, ways to resolve them); - chronological summary; - presentation from causes to effects (from particular to general); - inductive presentation (from general to particular). Various aspects are considered that contribute to a better understanding of the idea by the listeners. At the same time, it is very important not to overspend time, making sure to leave it for the conclusion. The development plan for the main part should be clear. The subject of the speech should be to open up

concretely and harmoniously. As many as possible should be selected factual materials and necessary examples.

3. Conclusion Conclusion is the formulation of conclusions that follow from the main purpose and main idea of the speech. A well-constructed conclusion contributes to a good impression of the performance as a whole. In conclusion, it makes sense to repeat the core idea and, in addition, to return (briefly) to those moments of the main part that aroused the interest of the listeners. You can end your speech with a decisive statement summarizing the speech.

Thus, the traditional definition sounds like this: rhetoric is the theory, skill and art of eloquence. In the classical sense, rhetoric, or oratory, is the science and art of preparing, constructing and publicly delivering a speech in order to have the desired effect on the audience.

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